

Micellar effect on the kinetics of acid catalysed bromination of some aromatic ketones

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The effect of anionic surfactant sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) on the kinetics of bromination of acetophenone and two *para*-substituted acetophenones (4-X-C₆H₄COCH₃, X = H, Cl, OMe) has been studied using bromine solution in 87% acetic acid at 35–50°. The concentration of SDS is varied and maintained beyond its critical micellar concentration. Perchloric acid has been used to catalyse the bromination and the reaction performed at a constant ionic strength using sodium perchlorate. The rate accelerates on increasing the concentration of SDS, HClO₄ and temperature following the sequence : *p*-chloro < unsubstituted < *p*-methoxy-acetophenone. The thermodynamic parameters for the reaction have been evaluated.

Reports are available on the kinetics of halogenation of ketones¹. Bromination of acetophenones has been studied using molecular bromine catalysed by acid and bases^{2,3}. Literature reports the kinetics of iodination of acetophenones catalysed by acid and bases^{4,5}. Chlorination of ketones by hypochlorite in aqueous alkali has resulted unexpected products⁶. Selective monohalogenation of ketones has been performed with Se^{IV} oxyhalides⁷. But not much work have been done to find the effect of surfactant on halogenation of ketones. We reported earlier⁸ the effect of SDS micelles on iodination of acetophenones catalysed by base. The present work deals with the effect of anionic surfactant SDS on the bromination of *p*-substituted-acetophenones in presence of acid.

Results and Discussion

The effect of SDS in varying concentrations beyond its CMC, on the rate of bromination of three acetophenones at different [HClO₄] and temperature has been studied at fixed ionic strength in 87% acetic acid solution. The results are given in Tables 1–4. The bromination of ketones having α -hydrogen on the adjacent carbon in acid medium proceeds through enolisation and subsequent electrophilic addition to double bonds⁹. The mechanism is presented in Scheme 1.

Step 1 :

Step 2 :

R = 4-X-C₆H₄COCH₃ (X = H, Cl, OMe)

Scheme 1

The overall bromination reactions of acetophenone can be presented as

and the main product is either phenacyl bromide or *para*-substituted phenacyl bromide¹⁰ depending on the nature of R.

In the reaction (Scheme 1) H⁺ is a product which can catalyse the enolisation, hence it is an autocatalytic process. The kinetic data obtained were fitted to the rate expression meant for second order autocatalytic reaction and found to be in good agreement. Pattnaik *et al.*² studied the bromination of different substituted acetophenones and correlated the substituted effect with activation energy, dissociation constant of acetophenones and also with Hammett relationship.

Effect of anionic surfactant : It has been established that surfactant micelle either accelerates or retards the organic reactions depending on its nature. This happens due

to the electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions among substrates, reactants and micelles. As a result, distribution of the substrate in the bulk and micellar phase becomes uneven. The CMC of SDS with the present reaction composition (0.05 M perchloric acid with 0.841 M sodium perchlorate in 87% acetic acid) was determined by conductance measurement method¹¹ and found to be very close to 0.01 M. The observed value of second order rate constant (k_2) for the bromination in presence of increasing concentration of SDS (0.01 to 0.035 M), has gradually increased in case of acetophenone and two *para*-substituted-acetophenones in the sequence : *p*-chloro < unsubstituted < *p*-methoxy, at 40° (Table 1). The same order of reactivity was observed in acid-catalysed iodination of acetophenones⁴. The cause of rate acceleration is the solubilisation of acetophenones in anionic micelles of SDS due to hydrophobic interaction and easy availability of proton in Stern layer for enolisation. The addition of bromine to the enol is facilitated to some extent due to the negative charge of the head groups of SDS micelles. The sequence of reactivity can be explained considering the stability of carbocation formed by the protonation of acetophenones (Scheme 1). The carbocation is more stabilised by *para*-methoxy and less stabilised by *para*-chloro group due to their electron-donating and electron-withdrawing nature respectively, in comparison to the unsubstituted acetophenone.

The kinetic data of this study can be fitted to the distribution model developed by Menger and Portnoy¹² considering the progress of the reaction in bulk phase and micellar pseudo-phase as per Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

where S_n is the surfactant aggregate (micelle), A the acetophenone, $S_n A$ the micelle-acetophenone complex, K_a the association constant, and k_2^w and k_2^m are the second order rate constants for the bromination in the bulk phase and micellar pseudo-phase respectively. A mathematical relation based on the said model is

$$1/k_2 - k_2 = (1/k_2^w - k_2^m) + [N/K_a(k_2^w - k_2^m)]/C_D - \text{CMC} \quad (1)$$

where, k_2 is the observed rate constant, N the aggregation number, C_D the varying total concentrations of surfactant

and CMC the critical micelle concentration of SDS. Other notations are described earlier. The k_2 data with varying concentration of SDS observed, in case of the three acetophenones, were fitted to the above relation (1). Plots of $1/(k_2^w - k_2)$ vs $1/(C_D - \text{CMC})$ resulted straight lines. From the intercept and slope of the plots and using the aggregation number N (value¹³ of SDS to be 62), the constants K_a and k_2^m were evaluated to be 1240, 790, 330 and 9.29×10^{-4} , 8.35×10^{-4} , $58.30 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for unsubstituted, *p*-Cl and *p*-OMe-acetophenones respectively.

Table 1. Rate constants for acid-catalysed bromination of acetophenones with variation of [SDS] in 87% (v/v) acetic acid solution [Ketone] = 0.018 mol dm⁻³, [Bromine] = 0.009 mol dm⁻³, [ClO₄⁻] = 0.841 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.050 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 40 ± 0.1°

[SDS] mol dm ⁻³	$k_2 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
	Acetophenone	<i>p</i> -Cl acetophenone	<i>p</i> -OMe acetophenone
0.000	30.38 ± 0.01	26.44 ± 0.02	83.00 ± 0.02
0.010	32.76 ± 0.01	29.20 ± 0.02	87.86 ± 0.02
0.015	35.89 ± 0.01	32.44 ± 0.02	92.86 ± 0.02
0.020	40.04 ± 0.02	34.93 ± 0.02	101.11 ± 0.02
0.025	44.72 ± 0.02	38.24 ± 0.02	109.94 ± 0.03
0.030	47.64 ± 0.02	41.64 ± 0.02	119.18 ± 0.03
0.035	50.64 ± 0.02	44.71 ± 0.03	132.65 ± 0.03

Rate dependence on [HClO₄]: The rate of bromination of the acetophenones with varying concentration of perchloric acid in 87% acetic acid solution in presence of fixed [ClO₄⁻] at 40° was determined. It is observed that on increasing [HClO₄], the rate increases in absence and presence of 0.01 M SDS (Table 2) following similar trend as in presence of anionic surfactant and with respect to substituents. On increasing the perchloric acid concentration in the reaction mixture, the [H⁺] increases and enolisation is fa-

Table 2. Rate constants for acid-catalysed bromination of acetophenones with variation of [HClO₄] in 87% (v/v) acetic acid solution in absence and presence of 0.01 M SDS

[Ketone] = 0.018 mol dm⁻³, [Bromine] = 0.009 mol dm⁻³, [ClO₄⁻] = 0.841 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 40 ± 0.1°

[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	[SDS] mol dm ⁻³	$k_2 \times 10^5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$		
		Acetophenone	<i>p</i> -Cl- acetophenone	<i>p</i> -OMe- acetophenone
0.05	0.00	30.38 ± 0.01	26.44 ± 0.02	83.00 ± 0.02
	0.01	32.76 ± 0.01	29.20 ± 0.02	87.86 ± 0.02
0.06	0.00	39.57 ± 0.02	32.19 ± 0.02	95.62 ± 0.03
	0.01	44.67 ± 0.02	39.13 ± 0.03	108.67 ± 0.03
0.07	0.00	51.98 ± 0.03	41.73 ± 0.03	113.38 ± 0.04
	0.01	55.28 ± 0.03	47.70 ± 0.04	126.73 ± 0.04

Table 3 Effect of temperature on the rate constants of acid-catalysed bromination of acetophenones in 87% (v/v) acetic acid solution in absence of SDS and the thermodynamic quantities[Ketone] = 0.018 mol dm⁻³, [Bromine] = 0.009 mol dm⁻³, [ClO₄⁻] = 0.841 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.050 mol dm⁻³

Ketone	Temp ±0.1°	$k_2 \times 10^5$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{\ddagger b}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^{\ddagger b}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^{\ddagger b}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Acetophenone	35	17.50 ± 0.01	94	91.4	20.1	97.7
	40	30.08 ± 0.01				
	45	60.08 ± 0.02				
	50	92.48 ± 0.04				
<i>p</i> -Chloro-acetophenone	35	16.31 ± 0.01	73.6	71.1	86.8	97.8
	40	26.44 ± 0.02				
	45	41.10 ± 0.02				
	50	61.98 ± 0.03				
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-acetophenone	35	56.62 ± 0.01	77.4	74.9	64.2	94.7
	40	83.00 ± 0.02				
	45	137.22 ± 0.03				
	50	228.04 ± 0.06				

^bat 35°**Table 4** Effect of temperature on the rate constants of acid-catalysed bromination of acetophenones in 87% (v/v) acetic acid solution in presence of 0.01 M SDS and the thermodynamic quantities[Ketone] = 0.018 mol dm⁻³, [Bromine] = 0.009 mol dm⁻³, [ClO₄⁻] = 0.841 mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.050 mol dm⁻³

Ketone	Temp ±0.1°	$k_2 \times 10^5$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^{\ddagger b}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^{\ddagger b}$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^{\ddagger b}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Acetophenone	35	19.62 ± 0.01	91.7	89.1	26.8	97.4
	40	32.76 ± 0.01				
	45	64.68 ± 0.03				
	50	98.96 ± 0.04				
<i>p</i> -Chloro-acetophenone	35	18.49 ± 0.01	70.8	68.2	95.0	97.5
	40	29.20 ± 0.02				
	45	44.90 ± 0.03				
	50	66.61 ± 0.04				
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-acetophenone	35	60.17 ± 0.01	77.4	74.7	64.2	94.5
	40	87.86 ± 0.02				
	45	144.90 ± 0.03				
	50	241.62 ± 0.06				

^bat 35°

cilitated. Hence the rate of bromination is dependent upon acid concentration. Plots of log k_2 vs log [HClO₄] are straight lines, which is in support of direct participation of HClO₄.

Temperature effect and activation parameters : The rate of bromination increases with rise in temperature from 35 to 50° in absence and presence of 0.01 M SDS at 0.05 M [HClO₄] keeping the concentration of other components of

solvent the same as mentioned in Table 1. The activation energy and other thermodynamic quantities have been computed from Arrhenius plot, Eyring equation and other mathematical relations. The results are furnished in Tables 3 and 4. The activation energy, enthalpy and entropy values decrease in presence of 0.01 M SDS in comparison to these in absence of SDS for all the three acetophenones. It indicates better stabilisation of transition states in anionic surfactant medium. However, the differences in these values are very small in absence and presence of SDS for *para*-methoxy-acetophenone. The negative values of entropy of activation suggest more ordering of the transition states. In case of *para*-substituted-acetophenone the entropy values are relatively much lower than the unsubstituted one, and it is lowest in case of *p*-chloro compound. Perhaps all the environmental factors in the reaction medium have positive contribution towards rigidity of the transition state of *para*-compound. The free energy of activation values follow the trend, *p*-OMe < unsubstituted < *p*-Cl, which is in good agreement with the kinetic results.

Experimental

The acetophenones were purified by standard methods. SDS (Sisco Chem) was recrystallised before use¹⁴. Acetic acid was repeatedly refluxed with chromium trioxide and distilled. Perchloric acid (AnalaR) was diluted with triple-distilled water. Bromine and other chemicals were of reagent grade.

A solution of 0.05 M perchloric acid with 0.841 M sodium perchlorate was prepared in 87% acetic acid. It was used to dissolve acetophenones, bromine and SDS for obtaining solutions of appropriate concentration.

Rate measurements : A solution of acetophenones, SDS and bromine of appropriate concentration were preheated in a thermostat (± 0.01°) to attain the desired temperature. Then a mixture of acetophenones and SDS of required composition of 20 ml was prepared and thermostated. The reaction was initiated by adding 0.1 M bromine solution (2 ml) and shaken gently. The reaction was followed by quenching 2 ml of reaction mixture in 2 ml 0.04 M KI solution in molar sodium hydroxide at fixed time interval. The liberated iodine was estimated titrimetrically against standard sodium thiosulphate solution in presence of chloroform. The bromine solution was also standardised by the similar titrimetric method. Since the reaction is autocatalytic in nature (Scheme 1), the rate constant (k_2) was computed from the slope of the plot of log $\{(b+x)/(a-x)\}$ vs t using the special type of second order rate expression¹⁵,

$$k_2 = \{2.303/t(a + b)\} \log\{a(b + x)/b(a - x)\}$$

where a and b are the initial concentration of acetophenones and perchloric acid respectively, and x is the decrease in concentration of bromine after time t . All the rate constants are reported with standard deviations.

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